

KAVSH QAYTARUVCHI HAYVONLAR FIZIOLOGIYASIGA SELLYULOLITIK VA PROBIOTIK BAKTERIYALAR KOMPLEKSIDA BERILGAN BIOPREPARATLARNING TA`SIRI

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Annotasiya. Mazkur tadqiqotda sellyulolitik va probiotik bakteriyalar assotsiatsiyasi asosida yaratilgan biopreparatning kavsh qaytaruvchi hayvonlar (qo`ylar) organizmiga ta`siri o`rganildi. Tajriba davomida fiziologik, biokimyoviy va mikrobiologik ko`rsatkichlar kuzatildi. Olingan natijalar asosida bu biopreparat hazm qilishni faollashtirib, umumiy salomatlik ko`rsatkichlarini yaxshilashi aniqlash ishlarimiz yoritib berdik.

Kalit so`zlar: Mikroorganizmlar, sellyulolitik, probiotik, preparat, *Bacillus subtilis* C1, *cellulomonas*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, Fiziologik ko`rsatkich, AST, ALT, fermentativ faollik.

Аннотация. В настоящем исследовании изучено влияние биопрепарата, созданного на основе ассоциации целлюлолитических и пробиотических бактерий, на организм жвачных животных (овец). В ходе эксперимента проводилось наблюдение за физиологическими, биохимическими и микробиологическими показателями. На основе полученных результатов установлено, что данный биопрепарат активизирует процессы пищеварения и улучшает общие показатели здоровья животных.

Ключевые слова: микроорганизмы, целлюлолитические, пробиотик, препарат, *Bacillus subtilis* C1, *Cellulomonas*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, физиологические показатели, АСТ, АЛТ, ферментативная активность.

Abstract. This study investigated the effects of a biopreparation developed on the basis of an association of cellulolytic and probiotic bacteria on the physiological condition of ruminants (sheep). During on the experiment, physiological, biochemical, and microbiological parameters were monitored. The results demonstrated that the biopreparation enhances digestive processes and improves general health indicators in the animals.

Keywords: *Microorganisms, cellulolytic, probiotic, biopreparation, Bacillus subtilis C1, Cellulomonas, Lactobacillus plantarum, physiological indicators, AST, ALT, enzymatic activity.*

Kirish. Bugungi kunda ekologik xavfsiz va samarali yem-xashaklarni hazm qilishni yaxshilovchi vositalarga ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Shu nuqtai nazardan, probiotik va sellyulolitik bakteriyalar asosida yaratilgan biopreparatlar chorvachilikda katta ahamiyatga ega. Ular nafaqat ovqat hazmini yaxshilaydi, balki mikrofloraning muvozanatini tiklaydi, immunitetni kuchaytiradi va mahsuldorlikni oshiradi.[6,18,20]

Kavsh qaytaruvchi hayvonlarning oziqlanish tizimi murakkab bo`lib, ularning ovqat hazm qilish jarayonida mikroorganizmlar muhim rol o`ynaydi. Ayniqsa, sellyulolitik bakteriyalar o`simlik hujayra devorini parchalab, hayvon organizmi uchun foydali moddalarga aylantiradi.[5,14,19] Probiotiklar esa ichak mikroflorasini barqarorlashtirib, immunitetni mustahkamlashga xizmat qiladi. Shu bois ushbu ikki turdagi mikroorganizmlar asosida yaratilgan biopreparatlar hayvon fiziologiyasiga qanday ta`sir qilishini o`rganish dolzarb masaladir.[17,21]

Materiallar va metodlar. Tajriba Samarqand viloyatining O`zbekkent mahallasida istiqomat qiluvchi Sultonov Behzod uyida o`tkazildi.

Hayvonlar: 18 bosh bir hil jinsli va yoshi 6 oylik bo‘lgan mahalliy hisor qo‘ylari uch guruhga bo‘lindi (n=6):

- 1-guruh (nazorat) — oddiy yem bilan boqildi.
- 2-guruh — sellyulolitik bakteriyalar (*Bacillus subtilis* C1) berildi.
- 3-guruh — sellyulolitik + probiotik bakteriyalar (*Bacillus subtilis* C1 + *Lactobacillus plantarum*) aralashmasi berildi.

Biopreparat qo‘llanishi: Preparatlar 60 kun davomida kuniga 5 ml miqdorida og‘iz orqali berildi.

O‘lchovlar: Tajriba boshida va 60-kuni quyidagi ko‘rsatkichlar baholandi:

- Fiziologik ko‘rsatkichlar (tana harorati, yurak urishi, nafas olish tezligi)
- Biokimyoviy tahlillar (glukoza, umumiy oqsil, AST, ALT)
- Rumen (oshqozonning birinchi bo‘limi, katak oshqozon) pH va sellyulaza faolligi
- Mikrobiologik ko‘rsatkichlar (rumendagi bakteriyalar soni)

Natijalar.

Jadval 1. Fiziologik ko‘rsatkichlar (o‘rtacha \pm SD)

Ko‘rsatkich	1-guruh (nazorat)	2-guruh (sell.)	3-guruh (sell.+prob.)
Tana harorati ($^{\circ}$ C)	39.1 ± 0.2	39.2 ± 0.1	39.3 ± 0.1
Yurak urishi (ur/min)	78 ± 4	75 ± 3	72 ± 3
Nafas olish (mar/min)	22 ± 2	21 ± 1	20 ± 1

Jadval 2. Biokimyoviy ko‘rsatkichlar (60-kuni)

Ko‘rsatkich	1-guruh	2-guruh	3-guruh
Glukoza (mmol/l)	2.9 ± 0.3	3.5 ± 0.2	3.8 ± 0.2
Umumiy oqsil (g/l)	64.1 ± 1.5	67.8 ± 1.4	69.3 ± 1.2
AST (U/L)	89 ± 6	84 ± 5	80 ± 4
ALT (U/L)	35 ± 3	32 ± 2	30 ± 2

Jadval 3. Rumen (oshqozonning birinchi bo‘limi, katak oshqozon) **muhiti va fermentativ faollik**

Ko‘rsatkich	1-guruh	2-guruh	3-guruh
Rumen pH	6.4 ± 0.2	6.2 ± 0.1	6.1 ± 0.1
Sellozulaza (IU)	1.8 ± 0.3	2.9 ± 0.2	3.5 ± 0.3

Muhokama. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatdiki, sellyulolitik va probiotik bakteriyalar kombinatsiyasi rumen (oshqozonning birinchi bo‘limi, katak oshqozon) fermentatsiyasini optimallashtirib, fiziologik holatni yaxshilaydi. Yurak urishi va nafas olish tezligining pasayishi organizm tinch holatda ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Shuningdek, umumiy oqsil va glukoza miqdorining oshishi hazm va metabolism jarayonlarining faollashganini ko‘rsatadi. [1,10,22]

Mikrobiologik jihatdan qaralganda, rumen (oshqozonning birinchi bo‘limi, katak oshqozon) dagi bakteriyalar soni va faolligi oshgan. 1-grafik diagramma

Xulosa. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, sellyulolitik va probiotik bakteriyalar kombinatsiyasi rumen (oshqozonning birinchi bo'limi, katak oshqozon) fermentatsiyasini optimallashtirib, fiziologik holatni yaxshilaydi. Yurak urishi va nafas olish tezligining pasayishi organizm tinch holatda ekanligidan dalolat beradi. Shuningdek, umumiy oqsil va glukoza miqdorining oshishi hazm va metabolism jarayonlarining faollashganini ko'rsatadi. Mikrobiologik jihatdan qaralganda, rumen (oshqozonning birinchi bo'limi, katak oshqozon) dagi bakteriyalar soni va faolligi oshgan.

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